

MISE-EN-PLACE AS A FOOD PREPARATION STRATEGY FOR WORKING CLASS HOMEMAKERS IN ABUJA FCT, NIGERIA

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Abstract:

The main purpose of this study was to examine “mise-en-place” as a food preparation strategy among working class homemakers in Abuja (FCT). To guide the study, three research questions and three null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 5% probability level. The design of the study was descriptive survey. The study was carried out in Abuja (FCT) of Nigeria. The population for the study was 8,128 homemakers working in banks and lecturers of tertiary institutions. The sample size for the study was 426. Simple random sampling technique was used to select Eleven (11) types of banks and Eight (8) tertiary institutions located across the Six Local Government Councils that constitute the population of the study. Proportionate Stratified Random Sampling Technique was used to select 300 Bankers present in selected sampled Banks and 126 Lecturers of tertiary institutions located across the Six Local Government Councils that constitute the population of the study. A structured questionnaire titled =“questionnaire on mise-en-place as a food preparation strategy among working class homemakers” (QMWCH) was used for data collection. The questionnaire has two parts and five sections. Part I, sought information on the personal data of the respondents. Part 2: Section A, B, C, and D sought information on the four objectives of the study. Section A – B was structured on a four (4) point rating Scale of Very Great Extent (VGE), Great Extent (GE), Low Extent (LE) and Very Low Extent (VLE). VGE – 4 points, GE – 3, LE – 2, and VLE – 1. While, Section C – D was structured on a four (4) point rating Scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). SA – 4 points,

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A – 3, D – 2, and SD – 1. Reliability of QMWCH was obtained using Cronbach alpha formula. The internal consistency was 0.85. The instrument was face validated by 2 experts from the Department of Home Economics and Hospitality Management Education, Faculty of Vocational and Technical Education, University of Nigeria, Nsukka and one expert from the Department of Measurement and Evaluation, University of Nigeria, Nsukka. Mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions while, t– test was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that 300 Bankers selected for the study utilize “mise-en-place” in food preparation on the Low Extent (LE), but for the 126 Lecturers, selected for the study, it was on a Great Extent (GE). Bankers and Lecturers adopt “mise-en-place” in the Serving of Food to Family Members to a Great Extent (GE). Meanwhile, Bankers and Lecturers Agreed on the twelve challenges involved in using “mise-en-place” as a food preparation strategy among working class homemakers. Working class homemakers working in Banks and those Lecturing differ significantly in their responses on the utilization of “mise-en-place” in food preparation. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended among others that: (i) Working class Homemakers working in banks and lecturers of tertiary institutions should adopt the utilization of “mise-en-place” in food preparation. (ii) Lecturers should put more effort to the teaching and learning of “mise-en-place” as a strategy in food preparation.

Keywords: mise-en-place, food preparation strategy, working class homemakers

1. Introduction

Human existence depends on the routine activities that feeding, clothing, shelter and care for the children and adults can provide. These activities are all performed in the home. A home is a house in which a family lives. Anyakoha (2013) postulates that a home is an abode or dwelling place for a family. According to Anyakoha a home is a place where family members can do many things together such as share their interest, activities, joy, love and work together for the benefit of each other and the whole family and prepare food and eat together. In a nutshell, a home is a place family needs are met.

The homemaker is someone in charge of the home. Dimelu (2010) perceives a homemaker as a person in the family especially a woman whose main responsibility is to take care of the family members and their menu. A working class homemaker is one who engages in a paid employment outside her home. She may be employed either in a white or blue collar job. According to Edsall (2012), white collar jobs do not require wearing of work clothes or protective clothing while blue collar jobs require wearing of work clothes or protective clothing. Thus a working class homemaker is a person who works in any of all those white and blue collar jobs, manual, mental workers of all types excluding individuals that derive, their income from business ownership. It is interesting to note that majority of the homemakers in the Federal Capital Territory (FCT Abuja) are working class. Some of them are wage earners while others are self employed. Douglas (2010)

stated that a working class homemaker works for forty (40) hours or more per week outside the home and usually in profession that is career oriented such as lawyers, medical personnel, teachers lecturers, bankers, chief executive officers and administrators among others. Due to the high cost of living especially in terms of accommodation, education and feeding of family members, majority of the homemakers need to work to earn more income to support the family.

Mise-en-place is a French phrase meaning advance preparation in order to meet up with time. Mise-en-place is a strategy that can be adopted in the home in food preparation by a working class homemaker. The working class homemaker is in 'dilemma' meeting up with the demand of her work outside the home and the preparation of nutritious meals for her family members on time. David (2007) posits that 'mise-en-place' would ensure that service times are met and a high quality meal can be achieved. The working class homemaker using 'mise-en-place' can plan her meals several days or weeks ahead of time. 'Mise-en-place' can be likened to the management principles of planning, organizing, implementing and evaluating the use of time in order to accomplish or perform certain tasks or duties. Anyakoha and Eluwa (2010) postulated that through the application of management principles, individuals and families can utilize their resources effectively to achieve the desired qualities of life.

Food preparation in the home simply means all the activities one might perform to make food ready to be eaten. Sumati (2012) observed that food preparation is the process of using heat to prepare food for the consumption of man. It is not enough that food be nutritious, it has to be pleasing in appearance and tasteful as it is eaten.

Sumati (2012) stressed that good food preparation is an important prerequisite of food acceptance. Therefore, it is important to acquire the ability to prepare and serve food which is nutritious and acceptable to the family. Since the science of food preparation is based on the understanding of the physical and chemical changes that occur in food during preparation. Ene-Obong (2001) opined that this knowledge can be used to combine food ingredients with delicate flavours, textures and colours delight the sense organs.

Planning and organizing "mise-en-place" is a necessary strategy every working class homemaker must practice. David (2007) buttressed the fact that even on the simplest level, preparation is necessary. He stressed that in every recipe the following must be done:

- 1) assembling of tools;
- 2) assembling of ingredients;
- 3) washing, trimming, cutting, preparing and measuring of raw materials.

Since the working class homemaker returns home late from work, tired and exhausted and still have to face the strenuous activities of food preparation, David (2007) suggested that there is far too much work to do in the kitchen to leave until the last minute, hence some work must be done in advance. In order to solve the problems facing the working class homemaker, she must plan pre-preparations carefully. Sumati et al defined food as anything eaten or drunk which meets the need for energy building,

regulation and protection of the body. The author opined that intake can ensure good nutrition and health.

Meal planning involves making decision on what to eat daily at each meal. Family members are not always the same. They are different in age, sex, health, occupation and their nutritional needs. Anvakoha and Eluwa (2010) stated that meal planning is the process of designing adequate balanced meals in which all the essential nutrients are presents in the right proportion for specific groups of people. A well planned meal therefore should meet the nutritional needs of an individual thereby promoting health.

People generally spend a Jot of money on food and its preparation. Therefore, Anyakoha and Eluwa suggested that 30% of the family income should be spent on food. The money available to a family will determine the type of foods they can afford. The food budget of the high-income families is different from that of low income families.

Anyakoha and Eluwa suggested the following steps in making a budget:

- list all the commodities (food) needed by the family members throughout the period of the proposed budget.
- make an estimate of the cost of the foods.
- estimate the total expected income for the family during the planned period.
- bring the expected income and expenditure into balance.
- check the budget to ensure that it is likely to succeed.

An adequate diet is one that provides all of the essential nutrients in sufficient quantities for a given individual. Ene-Obong (2001) proposed a basic six (6) food pyramid for Nigeria. These groups are:

- group 1: starchy roots tubers fruits cereals;
- group 2: meat and legumes. nuts and seeds;
- group 3: fats and oils;
- group 4: vegetables;
- group 5: fruits;
- group 6: other foods (herbs, spices, condiments).

Ensuring adequate diet that comprises all the groups in the food pyramid requires a lot of planning and preparation especially for a working class homemaker. It is the need to ensure adequate preparation and planning that has stimulated this study on mise-en-place.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

In recent years there has been increasing focus on the question of how to balance work and family life of women in academics and banking industry. Homemaking is one initiative that has been promoted as a way of improving the work-life balance. Food preparation entails a lot of activities, which makes it cumbersome, energy draining, time consuming and challenging for working class homemakers in Abuja. A working class homemaker works for 40 hours or more per week outside her home as a career woman. She is still required to provide nutritious meals for her family member at the right time. In most cases, working class homemakers, due to their multiple responsibilities, return

from work to prepare nutritious food for family members could expose them to a lot of stressful conditions. These developments have accelerated concerns over health and fitness status of homemakers who combine work and family responsibilities. Changing family and work structure in Nigeria makes coping with work and family roles challenging for women to handle. When an employee invests larger portion of time at work, the time available for family or other non work roles is reduced. Since the working class homemakers play multiple roles in the family and still maintain their employment outside their home, it becomes imperative that they be educated in ways that could help them to reduce the time spent on food preparation, thus ensuring that family meals are served at the right time.

Despite the efforts that working class homemakers are making to meet the family needs and work responsibilities outside the home, it appears that the efforts are not yielding the desired result. It is of interest to the researcher therefore, to examine the challenges that women face in the bid to combine these responsibilities. How contemporary women combine career and family life, and the way in which they solve competing demands, becomes of increasing importance as great number of women enter the labour force.

As this trend becomes the norm, this subject becomes of increasing practical interest and presents a need for additional research to examine the extent of the use of “mise-en-place” strategies that is adopted by working class homemakers in food preparation in order to meet up with time.

1.2 Purpose of the Study

The major purpose of the study was to examine “mise-en-place” as a food preparation strategy among working class homemakers in Abuja (FCT).

Specifically, the study determined:

1. the extent to which working class homemakers utilize “mise-en-place” in food preparation.
2. the extent to which the working class homemakers adopt “mise-en-place” in the serving of food to family members.
3. the challenges involved in using “mise-en-place” by working class homemakers in food preparation.

1.3 Significance of the Study

The benefits that shall accrue from this study are many. Specifically, the following groups of people will benefit from the findings of this study: homemakers, teachers/lecturers of Home Economics, bankers, Home Economics’ students, government, guidance/counselors, Home Economics’ researchers, Home Economics organization and college/university libraries.

The findings of this study will provide information to the homemakers on the importance of “mise-en-place” as a strategy in food preparation through workshops, conferences and other women fora. Homemakers will utilize the knowledge from the

findings to prevent fatigue and stress in food preparation and balance the demand of their dual roles and have time for rest and leisure.

The findings of this study will be beneficial to Home Economics teachers/lecturers in every area of Home Economics through seminar and conferences by providing them with information on the use of “mise-en-place” as a food preparation strategy. They will use the information to prepare the students on the need for utilization of “mise-en-place” in food practical classes and for future homemaking. These experts can use the knowledge to provide handbook or manual on different preliminary treatment that can guide food preparation for homemakers.

The findings of this study will be of immense benefit to homemakers who work in the banking industry. They will learn how to plan their family meals well ahead of time in order to reduce stress and time used in food preparation.

On the part of the students, the findings of the study will inform them on the need to utilize “mise-en-place” in food preparation, to make their work easier and stress free. Based on this information the students can also impart the knowledge into upcoming generation and this can be achieved through student orientation programmes, and practical classes among others.

More so, the findings of this study will provide information to the government (Civil Service Commission and Ministries of Women Affairs) through public lectures, women affairs fora on the constraints and ways of improving on the constraints in carrying out food preparation. They will use this information to sensitize women in every woman fora.

Furthermore, the findings of the study will provide an empirical reference material for guidance and counseling educators as this will enhance their teaching/knowledge on the causes of stress and fatigue in food preparation in order to proffer appropriate stress management strategies to homemakers by organizing seminar, conferences and workshop for the public.

The findings will also provide useful resource materials for Home Economics researchers who are looking for information for their research. Home Economics organizations such as Home Economics Research Association of Nigeria (HERAN) will benefit from the findings of this study by using it as a handbook on how to reduce stress and time used in food preparation during its conferences. Lastly, college/university libraries will benefit from the findings of this study as future researchers consult it as a point of reference.

1.4 Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

- 1) To what extent do working class homemakers utilize “mise-en-place” in food preparation?
- 2) To what extent do working class homemakers adopt “mise-en-place” in the serving of food to family members?

- 3) What are the challenges involved in using “mise-en-place” by working class homemakers?

1.5 Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses for the study was tested at 0.05 level of significance.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of working class homemakers working in Banks and those Lecturing on the utilization of “mise-en-place” in food preparation?

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of working class homemakers working in Banks and those Lecturing on the adoption of “mise-en-place” in the serving of food to family members.

H₀₃: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of working class homemakers working in Banks and those Lecturing on the challenges involved in using “mise-en-place”.

1.6 Scope of the Study

The study was carried out at Abuja FCT, Nigeria. This study was delimited to “mise-en-place”, food preparation strategy, food service, challenges of using “mise-en-place” as food preparation strategy.

2. Method

2.1 Design of the Study

The descriptive survey research design was used for the study. According to Uzoagulu (2011), descriptive survey research design is one in which data is collected and analyzed from a few people or items considered to be representative of the entire group. The choice of this design was considered relevant because it permitted interaction with the object of the study.

2.2 Area of the Study

The study was conducted in Abuja, the Federal Capital Territory (FCT). Abuja is bounded on the north by Kaduna State, the West by Niger State, the East and South by Nassarawa State and the Southwest by Kogi State. The territory is currently made up of Six Local Councils, comprising the city of Abuja and five other Council's Areas namely: Abaji, Abuja Municipal, Gwagwalada, Kuje, Bwari and Kwali.

The reason for choosing these areas is because FCT is thickly populated with working class people most especially women (homemakers). Again, FCT has very busy road network that makes the traffic to be congested after closing hours from work. The traffic congestion makes the working class homemakers to return from work late.

2.3 Population for the Study

The target population was all the working class homemakers in Abuja (50,125) (HRD, 2016). The accessible population for this study was all working class homemakers in banks with a population of 5, 436 (HRD, 2016) and lecturers in tertiary institutions in Abuja with a population of 2,683 (ED, 2016). Thus, the total population of homemakers working in the banks and tertiary institutions was 8,128.

2.4 Sample and Sampling Techniques

The sample size for this study consisted of 426 homemakers working in banks and lecturers of tertiary institutions. Simple random sampling was used to select Eleven (11) types of banks and Eight (8) tertiary institutions located across the Six Local Councils that constitute the population of the study. The reason for the choice of simple random sampling technique was to ensure that each member of the population has an equal probability of being selected. Proportionate Stratified Random Sampling was used to select 300 Bankers present in selected sampled Banks and 126 Lecturers of tertiary institutions selected located across the Six Local Councils that constitute the population of the study. The reason was because this sampling technique ensures greater representativeness of the sample relative to the population.

2.5 Instrument for Data Collection

The instrument for the study is “Questionnaire on “Mise-en-place” as a food preparation strategy among working class homemakers” (QMWCH). The instrument was developed by the researcher after a review of the literature related to the study.

Based on the objectives of the study, the questionnaire was developed and structured into five sections.

- Part 1, sought information on the personal data of the respondents.
- Part 2: Sections A, B, C, and D sought information on the four objectives of the study:
 - Section A sought information on “mise-en-place” as a strategy in food preparation, with 16 items;
 - Section B sought information on “mise-en-place” as a strategy for food service with 4 items.
 - Section C sought information on the challenges involved in using “mise-en-place” as a food preparation strategy among working class homemakers with 12 items.
 - Finally, section D sought information on the challenges involved in using “mise-en-place” as a food service strategy among working class homemakers with 11 items.

Section A – B was structured on a four (4) point rating Scale of Very Great Extent (VGE), Great Extent (GE), Low Extent (LE) and Very Low Extent (VLE). VGE – 4 points, GE – 3, LE – 2, and VLE – 1. While, Section C – D was structured on a four (4) point rating

Scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). SA – 4 points, A – 3, D – 2, and SD – 1.

2.6 Validation of the Instrument

The QMWCH was face validated by two experts from the Department of Home Economics and Hospitality Management Education, Faculty of Vocational Technical Education, University of Nigeria Nsukka and one expert from the Department of Measurement and Evaluation, University of Nigeria, Nsukka. Their comments and suggestions bordered on the suitability of the items generated for the study. Language corrections and structural arrangement of items on the questionnaires, their suggestions and recommendations were incorporated into the final copy of the instrument.

2.7 Reliability of the Instrument

Thirty copies of the instrument were administered on 30 randomly selected working class homemakers (i.e. 15 Bankers and 15 Lecturers) for the trial testing of the instrument. Bankers and Lecturers from Nassarawa State Metropolis that were not among the sample of the study were used. This was to avoid bias and test-wise effect on the subjects.

After the trial testing, QMWCH was subjected to reliability analysis using Cronbach alpha formula. The internal consistency index obtained was 0.85. The choice of this reliability estimate was because the instrument has polytomously scored items i.e. each item of the instrument has no preferred answer (right or wrong).

2.8 Method of Data Collection

The researchers administered 426 copies of the instrument to the respondents with the help of three (3) research assistants. These research assistants were briefed on the objectives of the study and how to administer the questionnaire to the respondents.

The administration of the instruments was done once and retrieval was on the spot. Direct delivery was used in the administration and retrieval of the instrument, this was to minimize wastage.

2.9 Method of Data Analysis

The research questions were answered using Mean and Standard Deviation, and the null hypotheses were tested using t-test statistic at 0.05 level of significance

3. Results

The results of the study are presented in the tables that follow in the order of the research questions and hypotheses.

Research Question 1: To what extent do working class homemakers utilize “mise-en-place” in food preparation?

Table 1: Mean Ratings and Standard Deviation of Respondents on the extent to which working class homemakers utilize “mise-en-place” strategy in food preparation

S/N	Item Statement	Bankers (N= 300)			Lecturers (N=126)		
		$\bar{x}$	SD	Dec.	$\bar{x}$	SD	Dec.
1	Working class homemakers plan their family meals well ahead of time.	2.25	0.43	LE	2.64	0.48	GE
2	They know the principles involved in meal planning.	2.04	0.20	LE	2.98	0.15	GE
3	They do budgeting before buying their food stuff.	3.00	0.00	GE	2.64	0.48	GE
4	They buy their food stuff in quantity.	2.75	0.43	GE	2.60	0.49	GE
5	They have facilities for storing their food stuff to avoid spoilage/wastage.	2.78	0.41	GE	3.00	0.00	GE
6	They select their family meals according to the food groups.	2.27	0.44	LE	2.00	0.00	LE
7	They consider every member of their family before selecting meals that would suit them nutritionally.	2.22	0.41	LE	3.00	0.00	GE
8	They have acquired some basic cooking techniques like cake making, bread, meat pies, making of fruit juice, salads etc.	2.27	0.44	LE	2.76	0.43	GE
9	They have basic knowledge of cooking method e.g., boiling, frying, steaming, stewing, grilling and others.	2.01	0.10	LE	2.10	0.30	LE
10	They use the cooking method that conserves nutrients during food preparation.	2.25	0.43	LE	2.60	0.43	GE
11	They use modern facilities to cook their family meals (e.g. kerosene stove, gas cooker, pressure cook, microwave oven, blenders, pounding machine etc.).	2.94	0.23	LE	3.01	0.24	GE
12	They measure out the ingredients that will be used in meal preparation.	2.45	0.43	LE	2.20	0.00	LE
13	They assemble the equipment/facilities that would be used in meal preparation.	2.36	0.20	LE	2.40	0.00	LE
14	They prepare all the ingredients that would be used before the actual food preparation.	2.27	0.44	LE	2.00	0.00	LE
15	They organize their cooking step by step.	2.04	0.19	LE	2.02	0.00	LE
16	They clean up the kitchen and wash up the equipment/facilities before the real cooking.	2.27	0.45	LE	3.00	0.00	GE
Grand Mean		2.39	0.32	LE	2.56	0.18	GE

Note: Key: $\bar{x}$ = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation, Dec. = Decision

The result in Table 1 shows that the mean ratings of the extent to which bankers utilize “mise-en-place” in food preparation, on item numbers 1 – 2, 6 -16 to be 2.25, 2.04; 2.27, 2.22, 2.27, 2.01, 2.25, 2.94, 2.45, 2.36, 2.27, 2.04, and 2.27 with their corresponding standard deviation of 0.43, 0.20, 0.44, 0.41, 0.44, 0.10, 0.43, 0.23, 0.43, 0.20, 0.44, 0.19 and 0.45 respectively. Since the mean ratings are above 2.50 set as criterion level for accepting an item, it means the respondents agreed to a Low Extent (LE). The mean ratings of other items are as indicated.

Research Question 2: To what extent do working class homemakers adopt “Mise-en-place” in the serving of food to family members?

Table 2: Mean Ratings and Standard Deviation of Respondents on the Extent to which working class homemakers adopt “mise-en-place” in the Serving of Food to Family Members

S/N	Item Statement	Bankers (N= 300)			Lecturers (N=126)		
		$\bar{x}$	SD	Dec.	$\bar{x}$	SD	Dec.
1	Working class homemakers clean up the dining area before meals are served to family members.	2.95	0.22	GE	2.98	0.15	GE
2	They wash up the cutlery, plates, glasses, cruets and other equipments used in serving meals before the service time.	2.25	0.43	LE	3.00	0.00	GE
3	They lay the table with the necessary cutlery and accompaniment.	2.03	0.16	LE	3.00	0.00	GE
4	They prepare their deserts (fruits/fruit salads, ice creams, cream caramel and other foods taken at the end of a meal) in advance prior to the service of family members.	3.00	0.00	GE	3.00	0.00	GE
Grand Mean		2.56	0.27	GE	3.00	0.04	GE

Note: Key: $\bar{x}$ = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation, Dec. = Decision

The result in Table 2 showed the mean ratings of the extent to which bankers adopt “mise-en-place” in the Serving of Food to Family Members, on item numbers 1, 4 to be 2.95, 3.00 with their corresponding standard deviation of 0.22, 0.00 respectively. Since the mean ratings are above 2.50 set as criterion level for accepting an item, it means the respondents agreed to a Great Extent (GE). The mean ratings of other items are as indicated.

Research Question 3: What are the challenges involved in using “Mise-en-place” by working class homemakers?

Table 3: Mean Ratings and Standard Deviation of Respondents on the Challenges involved in using “mise-en-place” as a Food Preparation Strategy among Working Class Homemakers

S/N	Item Statement	Bankers (N= 300)			Lecturers (N=126)		
		$\bar{x}$	SD	Dec.	$\bar{x}$	SD	Dec.
1.	Working class homemakers do not plan their family meals in advance.	2.57	0.25	A	2.61	0.32	A
2.	They have no knowledge of principles involved in meal planning due to the nature of their careers.	2.25	0.43	D	2.01	0.09	D
3.	They have no knowledge of how to budget before buying their foodstuff.	2.98	0.14	A	2.00	0.00	D
4.	They do not buy foodstuff in bulk due to lack of space and or irregular payment of salaries.	2.02	0.13	D	3.00	0.00	A
5.	Some working class homemakers do not fully understand how to select adequate diets based on the food grouping.	2.97	0.16	A	3.00	0.00	A

6.	They do not consider the nutritional needs of every family member before planning their meals.	3.00	0.06	A	2.36	0.48	D
7.	Some have no basic techniques on how to prepare modern foods like cake, bread, salad, fried rice, fruit drinks etc.	3.97	0.20	SA	3.00	0.00	A
8.	Some working class homemakers know only a few cooking methods like boiling, frying and steaming.	2.25	0.43	D	3.00	0.21	A
9.	They do not possess modern equipment/facilities that would hasten their food preparation.	3.75	0.48	SA	2.00	0.00	D
10.	Most working class homemakers do not always assemble facilities/equipments used in food preparation before time.	3.00	0.00	A	2.76	0.43	A
11.	Most of them do not have the organizational ability during food preparation.	3.00	0.15	A	2.06	0.29	D
12.	They do not carry out pre-preparation of food items before the actual cooking.	2.98	0.17	A	3.00	0.22	A
Grand Mean		2.93	0.22	A	2.53	0.17	A

Note: Key: $\bar{x}$ = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation, Dec. = Decision

The result in Table 3 shows that the mean ratings of respondents on the challenges involved in using “Mise-en-place” as a food preparation strategy among working class homemakers. On item numbers 1, 3, 5, 6, 10 – 12, the mean ratings of 2.57, 2.98, 2.97, 3.00, 3.00, 3.00, 2.98 with corresponding standard deviation of 0.25, 0.14, 0.16, 0.06, 0.00, 0.15, 0.17, respectively shows that bankers agreed (A) but, strongly agreed (SA) on item 7 and 9 having the mean rating of 3.97 and 3.75 and standard deviation 0.20 and 0.48. Since the mean ratings are above 2.50 set as criterion level for accepting an item. The mean ratings of other items are as indicated.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of working class homemakers working in Banks and those Lecturing on the utilisation of “mise-en-place” in food preparation?

Table 4: t-test analysis of the mean response of working class homemakers working in banks and those Lecturing on the utilization of “mise-en-place” in food preparation

S/N	Item Statement	Banker =300, Lecturer = 126						
		Status	$\bar{x}$	SD	t-cal	Df	Sig.	Dec
1	Working class homemakers plan their family meals well ahead of time.	Bankers	2.25	0.43	-8.35	424	0.00	S
		Lecturers	2.64	0.48				
2	They know the principles involved in meal planning.	Bankers	2.04	0.20	-47.77	424	0.10	NS
		Lecturers	2.98	0.15				
3	They do budgeting before buying their foodstuff.	Bankers	3.00	0.00	12.88	424	0.00	S
		Lecturers	2.64	0.48				
4	They buy their food stuff in quantity.	Bankers	2.75	0.43	3.31	424	0.00	S
		Lecturers	2.60	0.49				
5	They have facilities for storing their food stuff to avoid spoilage/wastage.	Bankers	2.78	0.41	-5.89	424	0.00	S
		Lecturers	3.00	0.00				

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6	They select their family meals according to the food groups.	Bankers	2.27	0.44	6.75	424	0.00	S
		Lecturers	2.00	0.00				
7	They consider every member of their family before selecting meals that would suit them nutritionally.	Bankers	2.22	0.41	-21.29	424	0.00	S
		Lecturers	3.00	0.00				
8	They have acquired some basic cooking techniques like cake making, bread, meat pies, making of fruit juice, salads etc.	Bankers	2.27	0.44	-10.64	424	0.22	NS
		Lecturers	2.76	0.43				
9	They have basic knowledge of cooking method e.g., boiling, frying, steaming, stewing, grilling and others.	Bankers	2.01	0.10	-4.45	424	0.00	S
		Lecturers	2.10	0.30				
10	They use the cooking method that conserves nutrients during food preparation.	Bankers	2.25	0.43	-7.29	424	0.00	S
		Lecturers	2.60	0.43				
11	They use modern facilities to cook their family meals (e.g. kerosene stove, gas cooker, pressure cook, microwave oven, blenders, pounding machine etc.).	Bankers	2.94	0.23	-2.61	424	0.05	S
		Lecturers	3.01	0.24				
12	They measure out the ingredients that will be used in meal preparation.	Bankers	2.45	0.43	-6.41	424	0.00	S
		Lecturers	2.20	0.00				
13	They assemble the equipment/facilities that would be used in meal preparation.	Bankers	2.36	0.20	-2.29	424	0.00	S
		Lecturers	2.40	0.00				
14	They prepare all the ingredients that would be used before the actual food preparation.	Bankers	2.27	0.44	-18.57	424	0.00	S
		Lecturers	2.00	0.00				
15	They organize their cooking step by step.	Bankers	2.04	0.19	1.13	424	0.02	S
		Lecturers	2.02	0.00				
16	They clean up the kitchen and wash up the equipment/facilities before the real cooking.	Bankers	2.27	0.45	18.41	424	0.00	S
		Lecturers	3.00	0.00				
Cluster t		Bankers	2.39	0.32	-93.08	424	0.02	S
		Lecturers	2.56	0.18				

Result in Table 4 showed the t-test analysis of the significance difference in the mean response of working class homemakers working in Banks and those Lecturing on the utilization of “mise-en-place” in food preparation. Result showed that item 1, 3-7, and 9-16 is significant. The results of the test of other items are as indicated in the table.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of working class homemakers working in Banks and those Lecturing on the adoption of “mise-en-place” in the serving of food to family members.

Table 5: t-test analysis of the mean response of working class homemakers working in Banks and those Lecturing on the adoption of “mise-en-place” in the serving of food to family members (N=426)

S/N	Item Statement	Banker =300, Lecturer = 126						
		Status	$\bar{x}$	SD	t-cal	Df	Sig.	Dec.
1	Working class homemakers clean up the dining area before meals are served to family members.	Bankers	2.95	0.22	-1.23	424	0.01	S
		Lecturers	2.98	0.15				
2	They wash up the cutlery, plates, glasses, cruets and other equipments used in serving meals before the service time.	Bankers	2.25	0.43	-19.57	424	0.00	S
		Lecturers	3.00	0.00				
3	They lay the table with the necessary cutlery and accompaniment.	Bankers	2.03	0.16	-67.66	424	0.00	S
		Lecturers	3.00	0.00				
4	They prepare their deserts (fruits/fruit salads, ice creams, cream caramel and other foods taken at the end of a meal) in advance prior to the service of family members.	Bankers	3.00	0.00	14.25	424	0.00	S
		Lecturers	2.60	0.49				
Cluster t		Bankers	2.56	0.27	-74.21	424	0.00	S
		Lecturers	3.00	0.04				

Result in Table 5 showed the t-test analysis of the significant difference between the mean responses of working class homemakers working in Banks and those Lecturing on the adoption of “mise-en-place” in the serving of food to family members. Result showed that items 1-4 are significant. The results of the test of other items are as indicated in the table.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of working class homemakers working in banks and those lecturing on the challenges involved in using mise-en-place.

Table 6: t-test analysis of the mean response of working class homemakers working in Banks and those Lecturing on the challenges involved in using “mise-en-place”

S/N	Item Statement	Banker =300, Lecturer = 126						
		Status	$\bar{x}$	SD	t-cal	Df	Sig.	Dec
1	Working class homemakers do not plan their family meals in advance.	Bankers	2.57	0.25	-1.55	424	0.00	S
		Lecturers	2.61	0.32				
2	They have no knowledge of principles involved in meal planning due to the nature of their careers.	Bankers	2.25	0.43	6.15	424	0.00	S
		Lecturers	2.01	0.09				
3	They have no knowledge of how to budget before buying their foodstuff.	Bankers	2.98	0.14	78.39	424	0.00	S
		Lecturers	2.00	0.00				

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4	They do not buy foodstuff in bulk due to lack of space and or irregular payment of salaries.	Bankers	2.02	0.13					
		Lecturers	3.00	0.00					
5	Some working class homemakers do not fully understand how to select adequate diets based on the food grouping.	Bankers	2.97	0.16					
		Lecturers	3.00	0.00					
6	They do not consider the nutritional needs of every family member before planning their meals.	Bankers	3.00	0.06					
		Lecturers	2.36	0.48					
7	Some have no basic techniques on how to prepare modern foods like cake, bread, salad, fried rice, fruit drinks etc.	Bankers	3.97	0.20					
		Lecturers	3.00	0.00					
8	Some working class homemakers know only a few cooking methods like boiling, frying and steaming.	Bankers	2.25	0.43					
		Lecturers	3.00	0.21					
9	They do not possess modern equipment/facilities that would hasten their food preparation.	Bankers	3.75	0.48					
		Lecturers	2.00	0.00					
10	Most working class homemakers do not always assemble facilities/equipments used in food preparation before time.	Bankers	3.00	0.00					
		Lecturers	2.76	0.43					
11	Most of them do not have the organizational ability during food preparation.	Bankers	3.00	0.15					
		Lecturers	2.06	0.29					
12	They do not carry out pre-preparation of food items before the actual cooking.	Bankers	2.98	0.17					
		Lecturers	3.00	0.22					
Cluster t		Bankers	2.93	0.22	190.28	424	0.02	S	
		Lecturers	2.53	0.17					

Result in Table 6 showed the t-test analysis of the significance difference in the mean response of working class homemakers working in Banks and those lecturing on the challenges involved in using mise-en-place. Results showed that items 1-11 are significant. Results of the test of other items are as indicated.

4. Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study are discussed in line with the specific purpose of the study as follows:

Findings on the extent to which bankers utilize “mise-en-place” in food preparation is on the Low Extent (LE). It was therefore shown that Bankers do not plan their family meals well ahead of time, knows little on the principles involved in meal planning. Findings on the extent to which lecturers utilize “mise-en-place” in food preparation is on the Great Extent (GE). They measure out the ingredients to be used in

meal preparation, assembling the equipment/facilities that would be used in meal preparation, organizing their cooking step by step, and many more. Plan their family meals well ahead of time, know the principles involved in meal planning, and use the cooking method that conserves nutrients during food preparation. Inference drawn therefore is that the working class homemakers working in Banks and those Lecturing differ significantly in their responses on the utilization of “mise-en-place” in food preparation. This study is in line with the findings of Mustafa, Nazamul& Mohammed (2015) on work-life balance of female garment workers in Bangladesh. The finding from the study shows that both family and job of the female garment workers in Bangladesh are affected due to work-life balance situation. The findings also show that family life is more affected because of their work. It was also revealed from the study that work interference with family is more of an issue than family interference with work. This study is related with the present study in the area of balancing work with family life. “mise-en-place” is a strategy that is suggested to working class homemakers to help them balance between work and food preparation at home. The study differs from the present one in the area of geographical location, population, sampling and sampling techniques used for the study.

Findings on the extent to which Bankers and Lecturers adopt “mise-en-place” in the Serving of Food to Family Members were to a Great Extent (GE). This showed that working class homemakers clean up the dining area before meals are served to family members, wash up the cutlery, plates, glasses, cruets and other equipments used in serving meals before the service time e.t.c. but much effort is needed to practice the adoption of “mise-en-place” in food preparation to a Very Great Extent. Working class homemakers working in Banks and those Lecturing differ significantly on their responses to the adoption of “mise-en-place” in the serving of food to family members. This study agreed with the findings of Ajayi (2013) who carried out a study on work-family balance among women in selected banks in Lagos state, Nigeria. The results of the study reveal that if work demand becomes heavy, the fact remains that marital roles cannot be shelved or neglected and tension between the two boundaries will require a compromise. Again the study shows that women will take the choice of keeping their family rather than work. The reviewed study is relevant to the present work because bankers and lecturers still adopt “mise-en-place” in the Serving of Food to Family Members were to a Great Extent. They chose to keep their family first, even if it is at the expense of their work.

Findings showed that Bankers and Lecturers Agreed on the challenges involved in using “mise-en-place” as a food preparation strategy among working class homemakers. Challenges like: lack of basic techniques on how to prepare modern foods like cake, bread, salad, fried rice, fruit drinks etc., Lack of modern equipment/facilities to hasten food preparation, Working class homemakers having no plan for their family meals in advance, Lack of full understanding on how to select adequate diets based on the food grouping, among others have been identified. The working class homemakers working in Banks and those Lecturing differ significantly in their responses on the challenges involved in using “mise-en-place”. This study is in agreement with Kalyani &

Mohanty (2014) who carried out a study on employee perception on work-life balance in hotel industry with reference to Odisha India. The findings of the study revealed that pressure of multiple roles, quality of health and even changing and abnormal working schedules are the major factors contributing to poor work-life balance in hotel industry in Odisha. The study relates to this present one in as to highlight some factor that contributes to poor work life which could in turn pose serious challenges to using “mise-en-place” as a food preparation strategy among working class homemakers. However, the difference is in the area of study. Also, a study was carried out by Hetanshi (2014) titled: An empirical study on work life balance and quality of life of working women in public and private sector, Gujarat-India. The objective of the study was to explore the work-life balance and quality of life among women employees of public and private sector. The study reveals that women in private sector are more often having anxiety related to their work-life balance. The study also found that women are more likely to feel sad and anxious because of stress than men. On the other hand, women in public sector are usually tired or depressed due to stressful life. The above study relates to the present study in that it discusses challenges of work-life balance and the quality of life of working women in public and private sector. However, the present study discusses challenges of using a “mise-en-place” strategy to balance between work-life and family life.

5. Conclusion

The major purpose of the study was to examine “mise-en-place” as a food preparation strategy among working class homemakers in Abuja (FCT). Data were collected, analyzed and interpreted. Based on the findings of the study conclusions were drawn; Homemakers that worked in Banks utilize “mise-en-place” in food preparation to a Low Extent, Homemakers that are Lecturers utilize “mise-en-place” in food preparation to a Great Extent. Homemakers working in Banks and Lecturers, adopt “mise-en-place” in the Serving of Food to Family Members was to a Great Extent. Homemakers working in Banks and Lecturers, Agreed on the challenges involved in using “mise-en-place” as a food preparation strategy among working class homemakers. Homemakers (i.e. Bankers) Strongly Agreed (SA) on the solutions to the challenges of using “mise-en-place” as a food preparation strategy. Findings showed that Lecturers also Agreed (A) on the solutions to the challenges of using “mise-en-place” as a food preparation strategy. Homemakers working in Banks and those Lecturing differ significantly in their responses on the utilization of “mise-en-place” in food preparation. Working class homemakers working in Banks and those Lecturing differ significantly on their responses to the adoption of “mise-en-place” in the serving of food to family members. The working class homemakers working in Banks and those Lecturing differ significantly in their responses on the challenges involved in using “mise-en-place”.

6. Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of the study:

- 1) Homemakers should adopt the utilization of “mise-en-place” in food preparation.
- 2) Teachers, lecturers and students of Home Economics should put more effort to the teaching and learning of “mise-en-place” strategy in food preparation.
- 3) Homemakers should adopt the use of “mise-en-place” in the Serving of Food to Family Members to a Very Great Extent.

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